

THE **BIODIVERSITY**
FOOTPRINT COMPANY

Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA) Methodology

Integrating Heterogeneous Ecosystem State Data into Biodiversity Footprint
Accounting

Version 1.1 | May 2026

This document is maintained as a living methodology and subject to periodic revision.

About This Report

This report is part of the Quality Biodiversity Footprints Technical Series. It accompanies the Working Paper “Measuring Ecosystem State for Biodiversity Footprints- Understanding Data Quality for Decision Making” which provides the broader conceptual and theoretical context. It is intended to also stand alone as a practitioner reference. The outputs for MESA are directly compatible with the BD Protocol accounting framework (Endangered Wildlife Trust 2020)

Biodiversity footprint accounting requires ecosystem state information that is quantitative, reference-based, spatially explicit, and comparable across ecosystem types and assessment methods. In practice, ecosystem state data are produced by a wide range of methods that differ in indicators, spatial resolution, scoring scales, and reference benchmarks. While these data may be robust within their original contexts, they cannot be combined directly for accounting purposes.

This working paper describes the Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA), a methodology developed by The Biodiversity Footprint Company (TBFC) for integrating, translating, and standardising heterogeneous ecosystem state data into the inputs required by the Biological Diversity Protocol (BD Protocol). MESA is structured around five quality criteria for accounting-grade ecosystem state data, four data-source categories with explicit confidence levels, and broad scoring tables for terrestrial and freshwater realms used where comprehensive ecosystem-specific protocols are unavailable.

MESA outputs are expressed as state-adjusted surface areas (hectares equivalents, ha eq.), enabling transparent aggregation, loss-gain calculations, and tracking of No Net Loss / Net Positive Impact objectives across global operations.

The methodology is delivered in six steps: (1) delineating the assessment area; (2) determining original ecosystems; (3) delineating patches of uniform state; (4) scoring ecosystem state with associated confidence; (5) compiling the Ecosystem State Asset Inventory; and (6) monitoring changes over time when triggers occur.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	1
About This Report	1
Contributing authors	1
Suggested citation	1
Table of Contents	2
Acknowledgements	2
Acronyms	3
1 Purpose	4
2 Introduction	5
3 Requirements for ecosystem state data for biodiversity footprints	6
4 Consolidating different ecosystem state data sources	8
Types of ecosystem state data inputs:	8
5 Assessing ecosystem state in the absence of data	10
6 Transparency and confidence in data use	14
7 Converting different assessment metrics	15
8 STEPS FOR MESA	17
Step 1. Delineation of assessment area	18
Step 2. Determine original ecosystems	18
Step 3. Delineate uniform state and disturbance	19
Step 4. Score ecosystem state	20
Step 5. Create Ecosystem State Asset Register	21
Step 6. Monitor changes in state over time when triggers occur	21
9 Glossary	22
10 References	24
About The Biodiversity Footprint Company	25

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BD Protocol - Biological Diversity Protocol
BF - Biodiversity Footprint
BII - Biodiversity Intactness Index
CBD - Convention on Biological Diversity
EBV - Essential Biodiversity Variable
ESRS E4 - European Sustainability Reporting Standard E4
EVI - Enhanced Vegetation Index
GBF - Global Biodiversity Framework
GIS - Geographic Information System
GRI - Global Reporting Initiative
ha eq. - Hectares equivalents (state-adjusted surface area)
ICMM - International Council on Mining and Metals
IOM - Input-Output Models
IUCN - International Union for Conservation of Nature
IUCN GET - IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology
KBA - Key Biodiversity Area
LCA - Life Cycle Assessment
MESA - Manual Ecosystem State Assessment
MSA - Mean Species Abundance
NBF - Negative Biodiversity Footprint
NCA - Natural Capital Accounting
NDVI - Normalised Difference Vegetation Index
NNL - No Net Loss
NPI - Net Positive Impact
PBF - Positive Biodiversity Footprint
PES - Present Ecological State
TBF - Total Biodiversity Footprint
TBFC - The Biodiversity Footprint Company
TNFD - Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures

1

PURPOSE

The Biodiversity Footprint Company (TBFC) developed the Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA) to address the absence of a consistent framework for integrating ecosystem state data derived from diverse assessment methods into biodiversity footprint accounting. The methodology also responds to a common practical challenge: the need to conduct structured, defensible biodiversity footprint assessments in contexts where comprehensive monitoring data are unavailable.

By enabling heterogeneous and incomplete datasets to be interpreted within a common reference-based scoring system and expressed as surface area equivalents (ha eq.), MESA supports transparent aggregation, loss–gain calculations, and tracking of No Net Loss / Net Positive Impact objectives across global operations. It produces data directly for rigorous biodiversity accounting as per the BD Protocol. In doing so, it removes a key technical barrier to implementing site-level biodiversity footprint assessments and allows results to be progressively refined as improved data become available.

The Manual Ecosystem State Assessment (MESA) is a structured method for integrating, translating, and standardising ecosystem state information from multiple data sources for use in biodiversity footprint accounting (Figure 2.1). MESA accommodates ecosystem state inputs derived from ecosystem-specific field assessments, existing monitoring programmes, manual interpretation of remotely sensed imagery, and automatic or model-based classification approaches. Its purpose is to enable comparable, area-based ecosystem state metrics for loss–gain accounting (including No Net Loss reporting) and aggregation across sites, rather than to replace detailed ecological field assessments.

Biodiversity footprint accounting requires ecosystem state information that is quantitative, on a scale with a reference state, spatially explicit, and comparable across ecosystem types and assessment methods. In practice, ecosystem state data are generated using heterogeneous methods that differ in indicators, spatial resolution, scoring scales, and definitions of reference state. While these data may be robust within their original contexts, they are not directly comparable for accounting purposes. MESA provides a common interpretive and translation framework that allows diverse ecosystem state inputs to be expressed within a consistent ecosystem state scoring system and converted into surface area equivalents for accounting.

MESA functions as an accounting-oriented assessment and data integration framework that prioritises conceptual consistency, traceability, and transparency over procedural prescription. Where best-practice ecosystem-specific state measurement protocols are available, their results are incorporated directly. Where such protocols are unavailable or incomplete, MESA supports structured inference of ecosystem state using available spatial data and/or expert interpretation. Different data sources are associated with different levels of confidence (see Section 6), which are explicitly recorded alongside ecosystem state and form an integral part of the transparent application of MESA outputs in biodiversity accounting (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. Overview of the full biodiversity footprint process with MESA as Step 2.1

REQUIREMENTS FOR ECOSYSTEM STATE DATA FOR BIODIVERSITY FOOTPRINTS

While ecosystem science provides a wide array of detailed and context-specific methods for measuring ecological condition, MESA applies a pragmatic approach suited to biodiversity footprint accounting. Drawing on the Essential Biodiversity Variables framework (see Section 2.4 in *Measuring Ecosystem State for Biodiversity Footprints*), MESA evaluates ecosystem state through three foundational components: composition, structure, and function, assessed relative to a defined reference state.

Ecosystem assessment methods may differ in scale, indicators, and measurement techniques, but they ultimately capture one or more aspects of these three dimensions. For example, BioCondition (Eyre. *et al.* 2015), widely applied in Queensland, Australia for terrestrial ecosystem state assessments, integrates both compositional and structural attributes to determine ecosystem state.

While ecological assessment methods are designed to measure ecosystem condition, biodiversity footprint accounting imposes additional structural requirements on how that information must be defined. Ecosystem state data must support aggregation across sites and ecosystem types, enable comparison over time, and be transparently traceable to a defined spatial unit. MESA therefore applies explicit quality criteria to determine the validity of different ecosystem state data sources for biodiversity accounting (Table 3.1). These five criteria inform the confidence level assigned to state assessments (see Section 6).

Table 3.1. Quality criteria for ecosystem state data used in biodiversity footprint accounting.

Criterion	Requirement for Biodiversity Accounting	Examples of Data Not Meeting Criterion
Ecosystem-specific	Data must be relevant to the specific original ecosystem type and realm being assessed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Broad ecoregion-level assessments applied uniformly across terrestrial and freshwater components. ▶ Data without being specific to an ecosystem e.g. naturalness indices that do not distinguish ecosystems ▶ Data that measures an anthropogenic derived ecosystem such as a planted forest.
Quantitative and reference-based	Data must provide a quantitative score relative to a defined reference state, where the maximum score represents the reference condition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Qualitative state classes such as “good”, “moderate”, or “degraded” without defined numerical thresholds. ▶ Species lists without reference to expected assemblages. ▶ Tree density or vegetation cover measurements without reference benchmarking. ▶ Compliance status (e.g. “within permit limits”) that does not reflect ecological condition relative to reference.
Reflects ecosystem end- state (not drivers or land-use)	Data must capture the actual ecological state of the ecosystem rather than indirect drivers or management actions. Ecological state should also not be related to land-use.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Monitoring reports detailing rehabilitation activities (e.g. hectares planted) rather than ecological outcomes. ▶ Alien plant clearing effort reports without measuring resulting ecosystem recovery. ▶ Grazing capacity assessments focused on agricultural productivity rather than biodiversity. ▶ Water chemistry data without evaluating aquatic ecological response.
Area-based	Data must represent a defined spatial unit of uniform state(e.g., polygon).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Point-based water quality measurements not linked to mapped river reaches. ▶ Linear transect data not translated into mapped polygons of uniform state. ▶ Single quadrat surveys extrapolated to entire ecosystems without spatial delineation.
Timely	Data must be valid for the assessment year, reflecting recent material changes and seasonal dynamics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Monitoring data older than the assessment year without verification of unchanged state. ▶ Baseline surveys used for ongoing reporting. ▶ Remote sensing imagery mosaiced from multiple years. ▶ Seasonal surveys conducted outside ecologically relevant periods (e.g. dry-season vegetation surveys in seasonal wetlands without accounting for variability).

CONSOLIDATING DIFFERENT ECOSYSTEM STATE DATA SOURCES

MESA is designed to operate as a data-inclusive ecosystem state assessment system, capable of incorporating ecosystem state information derived from a wide range of data sources. These data sources vary substantially in their ecological specificity, spatial resolution, methodological rigour, and intended purpose. Rather than privileging a single type of input, MESA provides a structured framework through which diverse ecosystem-specific data can be interpreted, standardised, and translated into a common ecosystem state metric suitable for biodiversity net impact accounting (Table 4.1).

Types of ecosystem state data inputs:

Ecosystem-specific field-based assessment protocols:

These include best-practice ecological surveys and monitoring protocols developed for specific ecosystem types (e.g. coral reefs, grasslands, wetlands, forests), often implemented by accredited or trained specialists. Where available, such data provide the highest ecological resolution and can be incorporated directly into MESA provided all five quality criteria are met (Section 2).

Existing field monitoring and compliance data:

Many sites generate ecological or environmental monitoring data for regulatory, operational, or rehabilitation purposes (e.g. vegetation condition scores, wetland health assessments, rehabilitation performance indicators, species compositional data). Although these data are often not designed for biodiversity accounting, MESA enables their structured interpretation and, where appropriate, translation into ecosystem state scores (See Section 7 for converting different metrics). Existing site monitoring usually scores higher in confidence than just visual inspection, depending on which criteria are met (Table 6.1).

Manual desktop assessment using remotely sensed imagery:

Where field-based biodiversity data are unavailable or incomplete, MESA supports the manual interpretation of recent high-resolution satellite imagery, supplemented by available contextual information. This approach relies on trained ecologists to assess ecosystem functional integrity, fragmentation, connectivity, and visible anthropogenic disturbance using a defined ecosystem state scoring framework (see Section 5).

Automatic classification or model-based indices:

Ecosystem state information derived from desktop automatic classification through machine-learning models, rules-based classifications, or other available indices. These approaches typically offer high spatial coverage and consistency but lower ecological specificity and are therefore associated with lower

confidence levels. Table 6.1 in Section 6 shows the confidence levels (from acceptable to best) for the four main categories of ecosystem state data used for biodiversity accounting.

Table 4.1 illustrates how field-based and desktop assessment approaches are translated into standardised Broad Ecosystem State Scoring tables (0-6) (Tables 5.1 and 5.2) for integration into biodiversity accounting in line with the BD Protocol.1

Table 4.1. Comparison of the four main data sources for biodiversity accounting that can be combined, either as direct input or translated within MESA.

	Best-practice field monitoring	Desktop manual assessment and	Existing field monitoring/ compliance data	Automatic or model-based indices
Input into Biodiversity Accounting	Directly Applicable in MESA	Translation and Expert Interpretation into MESA.		Standardised indicators in MESA
Inputs	Monitoring protocols of state for specific ecosystems at a fine scale (e.g. coral reefs, arid grasslands, subtropical thicket).	Mixture of ground-based monitoring designed for other purposes (e.g. WUL monitoring, rehabilitation quality scores) and subjective expert-classification through visual assessment of remotely sensed imagery		Uses objective algorithms of structured input data with high scalability and consistency but lower ecological detail e.g. Machine Learning or other AI models.
Scoring metric	Each will have its own criteria / metric, scale (e.g. 0 to 5, 0 -1 or 1 to 10) and way of defining a reference state (no standardisation).	Existing monitoring will have its own criteria/metric scale but need to be translated into standardised scoring tables. Visual manual assessment will use standardised scoring tables.		May either be used directly in MESA if quantitative to a reference state, or need to be translated into standardised scoring tables.
Accounting criteria met	All criteria met. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Quantitative relative to the reference state, ✓ Area-based to determine patch size per state score ✓ Timely ✓ End-State not drivers/proxies 	Some criteria met. Subjective expert judgment.		Limited criteria met. Post-hoc manipulation of rules to down-weight regions of high extinction rates.
Accuracy for>NNL accounting.	Sensitive to changes in state (e.g. restoration) and accurate.	Sensitivity depends on ecological input data. Less accurate.		Sensitivity depends on input data. Least accurate.
Spatial Scale	Local (Global Ecosystem Typology levels 5-6).	Functional (Global Ecosystem Typology 3-6).		Global (Global Ecosystem Typology 1-2) Realm – Biome.

5

ASSESSING ECOSYSTEM STATE IN THE ABSENCE OF DATA

A key feature of MESA is that a meaningful ecosystem state assessment can still be undertaken in the absence of site-specific biodiversity field data. This is particularly important in early project stages, legacy operations, or regions where ecological surveys have not historically been conducted.

In such cases, ecosystem state can be inferred through desktop manual assessment, drawing on:

- ▶ freely available or low-cost public satellite imagery and spatial datasets;
- ▶ mapped original ecosystem extent and ecosystem type information;
- ▶ visible indicators of ecosystem transformation, degradation, fragmentation, and connectivity; and
- ▶ contextual knowledge of ecosystem structure, composition, and expected reference states.

This approach does not require proprietary biodiversity datasets. However, it does require interpretation by a trained ecologist with expertise in ecosystem processes, disturbance ecology, and landscape context. The role of the ecologist is to apply structured professional judgement within predefined ecosystem state categories, ensuring that assessments are ecologically defensible, consistent across sites, and transparent.

Where no ecosystem state measurement protocol is available at the site level, we source ecosystem state through broad scoring tables we have developed and adapted over time for terrestrial (Table 5.1) and freshwater realms (Table 5.2). Note: marine, subterranean and atmospheric realms are out of scope of the broad scoring tables in v1; for marine assessments TBFC relies on best-practice ecosystem-specific protocols.

These broad ecosystem scoring systems are based on two complementary concepts: (i) *functional integrity*, defined here as “the ecosystem’s current ability to maintain the structure and functions that define it, compared to its known or predicted reference state” (South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) 2022); and (ii) *ecological integrity* as defined by the IUCN’s Key Biodiversity Area Standard as “A condition that supports intact species assemblages and ecological processes in their natural state, relative to an appropriate historical benchmark, and characterised by contiguous natural habitat with minimal direct industrial anthropogenic disturbance” (IUCN 2016). Using these two approaches, we developed a broad terrestrial ecosystem state scoring system (Table 5.1), which uses available information on composition by considering the current known compositional assemblages of the specific ecosystem, and using indicators of structure and function by considering visible anthropogenic disturbance, and fragmentation based on patch size.

For the freshwater ecosystem state scoring system (Table 5.2), we based this on WET-Health from South Africa (Macfarlane *et al.* 2020) and the concept of Present Ecological State (PES) which refers to “*the perceived deviation from a theoretical reference condition, where the reference condition is defined as the un-impacted condition in which ecosystems show little or no influence of human actions*”. Whilst wetland features vary considerably from one wetland to the next, wetlands are all broadly influenced by their climatic and geological setting and by three core inter-related drivers, namely hydrology, geomorphology and water quality influencing the PES. While indicators of these are often not visible in satellite imagery alone, we used the broad descriptions of impact categories from WET-Health in our scoring table as indicators.

For consistency in undertaking subjective and rule-based scoring, we provide technical guidance, and/or training to our assessors in key aspects, including interpreting site monitoring data, identifying disturbances from satellite imagery and recognising the expected reference structure and composition of assessed ecosystems. Section 6 describes the accuracy implications of using different ecosystem state data sources.

Loxodonta africana. African savanna elephant. Botswana (EN)

Table 5.1. Broad terrestrial ecosystem state scoring system, used where comprehensive ecosystem-specific state measurement protocols are unavailable.

Ecosystem State		Indicators of Ecosystem State		
Score	Functional Integrity	Species assemblages and ecological processes	Indicators of industrial anthropogenic disturbance	Indicators of Fragmentation / Connectivity (contiguous natural habitat)
6	Reference State: historical benchmark	Fully intact ecological functions across all scales (from genes, species, communities, ecosystems to landscapes). No change in species assemblages (e.g. extinctions).	No change in natural ecosystem structure, processes and biota have occurred (e.g. extinctions).	Reflecting pre-industrial intactness. Large enough to maintain ecological communities through most natural disturbance events.
5.5	Reference State: present-day benchmark	Assumed fully intact ecological functions across most scales (e.g. gene-flow between isolated patches may be unknown).	Minimally affected by human disturbance.	Mostly intact natural communities and functioning broad-scale processes (e.g. wildfire, free-flowing rivers, and flooding patterns) and the natural movement patterns of species.
5	Very High	Mostly intact species assemblages that contain functional indicator species (species indicative of long-term structural stability, species sensitive to broad-scale ecological processes, area-demanding species).	No or minimal current anthropogenic disturbance (e.g. trails) with no signs of major or minor past disturbance (e.g., ploughing).	Very large (>1000 ha) intact area. High habitat connectivity serving as functional ecological corridors, with no roads or other linear infrastructure evident.
4.5			Minimal current anthropogenic disturbance (e.g. low livestock density)	Very large (>100 ha but <1000 ha) intact area. High habitat connectivity with limited road network between intact habitat patches.
4	High	Some loss of native species (e.g. large predators). Characteristic native biota present (i.e. the native species that define an ecosystem type and distinguish it from other ecosystem types.) Minimal invasive species.	Only minor current human disturbance (e.g. low livestock density) with no signs of major past disturbance (e.g. ploughing).	Large (>50 ha but <100 ha) intact area. Good habitat connectivity with potentially functional ecological corridors and a regularly used road network between intact habitat patches.
3.5			Only minor current human disturbance, with a few signs of minor past disturbance; moderate rehabilitation potential.	Medium to large (>20 ha but <50 ha) semi-intact area and a regularly used road network between intact habitat patches.
3	Medium	Some loss of native species (e.g. large predators, large densities of herbivores) and loss of characteristic native biota. Some alien and invasive species present.	Mostly minor current ecological impacts with some major impacts and a few signs of minor past disturbance, e.g. paths, selective logging, low-density infrastructure; moderate rehabilitation potential.	Medium (>10 ha but <20 ha) semi-intact area. Only narrow corridors of good habitat connectivity or larger areas of poor habitat connectivity; a busy used road network.
2.5			Several minor current and past human disturbance; low to moderate rehabilitation potential	Small to medium (>5 ha but <10 ha) area. Only narrow corridors of poor habitat connectivity; a busy used road network.
2	Low	Major loss of native species, including characteristic biota and functional indicator species). Well-established populations of alien and harmful invasive species.	Several minor and major current human disturbance e.g. fire suppression. Low rehabilitation potential.	Small (>1 ha but <5 ha) area. Almost no habitat connectivity but migrations still possible across some transformed or degraded natural habitat; a very busy used road network.
1.5			Several major past and minor current human disturbance in or around the area.	Small (>1 ha but <5 ha) area. Almost no habitat connectivity; a very dense and busy used road network.
1	Very Low	Complete loss of functional indicator species. Dominated by alien and invasive flora.	Several major current human disturbance in or around the area e.g. mining, harvesting, other infrastructure.	Very small (<1 ha) area. No habitat connectivity except for flying species or flora with wind-dispersed seeds.
0.05	Transformed-agriculture	Loss of ecological processes; dominated by a few agricultural species.	Monoculture agriculture / plantations	No habitat connectivity except for flying species or flora with wind-dispersed seeds.
0	Transformed-infrastructure	Complete loss of ecological processes.	Completely transformed e.g. mine, bare soil, buildings, road, quarry, etc.	Completely transformed

Table 5.2. Broad freshwater ecosystem state scoring system, used where comprehensive ecosystem-specific state measurement protocols are unavailable.

Ecosystem State		Indicators of Ecosystem State	Present Ecological State (PES) ¹		
Score	Functional Integrity	Species assemblages and ecological processes	Indicators of industrial anthropogenic modifications	PES Score	PES Category
6	Reference State: historical benchmark	Reflecting pre-industrial-level intact ecological functions and species assemblages.	No discernible modification to freshwater ecosystem	95-100%	A
5	Reference State: present-day benchmark	Unmodified, natural. Minimally affected by human disturbance. No change in freshwater ecosystem structure, processes and species.	Modification is such that it has no impact on freshwater ecosystem integrity	90-95%	A
4	Few modifications	A slight change in ecosystem processes is discernible, and a small loss of natural habitat and biota may have taken place.	Although identifiable, impact of this modification on freshwater ecosystem integrity is small.	80-89%	B
3	Moderate modifications	A moderate change in ecosystem processes and loss of natural habitats has taken place but the natural habitat remains predominantly intact.	The impact of modifications on freshwater ecosystem integrity is clearly identifiable but limited; approximately <25% affected.	70-79%	C
2	Large modifications	A large change in ecosystem processes and loss of natural habitat and biota has occurred.	The modification has a clearly detrimental impact on freshwater ecosystem integrity; Approximately 25-50% affected.	50-59%	D
1	Serious modifications	The change in ecosystem processes and loss of natural habitat and biota is great but some remaining natural habitat features are still recognizable.	The modification has a clearly adverse effect on this component of habitat integrity; approximately 50-75% freshwater ecosystem has been lost.	30-39%	E
0	Critical modifications/transformed	Ecosystem processes have been modified completely with an almost complete loss of natural habitat and biota.	The modification is present in such a way that the ecosystem processes of this component of wetland health are totally / almost totally destroyed.	0-19%	F
Examples of visible modification indicators:		Hydrology: water abstraction, upstream impoundments, stormwater inflow, artificial drainage, canalisation, hardening Geomorphology: sedimentation, erosion, infilling, excavation, trampling, road crossings, cultivation in wetland Vegetation: alien invasive species, overgrazing, clearing, mowing, altered fire regimes, terrestrial encroachment			

¹ South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) (2020). "Guidelines for the implementation of the Terrestrial Fauna and Terrestrial Flora Species Protocols for environmental impact assessments in South Africa." Species Environmental Assessment Guideline. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Version 3.1

TRANSPARENCY AND CONFIDENCE IN DATA USE

MESA explicitly records the confidence level associated with each ecosystem state input. Lower confidence data are not excluded from biodiversity accounting; rather, their limitations are transparently documented and can be considered in interpretation, reporting, and decision-making. The confidence levels are based on the accounting criteria in Section 3.

By accommodating a wide range of data sources - including situations where no biodiversity field data are available - MESA enables consistent ecosystem state assessment across diverse operational contexts, while maintaining clarity about the strengths and limitations of the underlying information.

Confidence ranges from best to acceptable (Table 6.1). For polygons which are visibly identifiable as completely transformed, scoring 0, the confidence is assigned as 'best'. For all other polygons, the confidence is based off monitoring data which fulfils criteria, or automatically assigned 'fair' if expert visual assessment of satellite imagery is the source. For automatic classifications (e.g. using satellite data, models, or global indices), which still fulfil the criteria ticked in Table 3.1, these score an 'acceptable level'. When automatic classification data are used, they may not always be accurate across an entire footprint assessment area. We give such data an acceptable confidence level for high-level risk assessments and we report where these results are used to inform decision-makers of the inherent uncertainty of the data.

Table 6.1. Confidence levels for ecosystem state data.

Data source	Confidence	Fulfils quality criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Quantitative relative to the reference state, ✓ Area-based to determine patch size per state score ✓ Timely ✓ End-state not drivers/proxies ✓ Ecosystem-specific
Comprehensive field data	Best	All criteria met.
Existing monitoring reports (for purposes other than biodiversity accounting, i.e. compliance)	Better	4/5 criteria met
	Good	3/5 criteria met
	Fair	2/5 criteria met (used in combination with manual classification)
Manual classification of recent satellite imagery	Fair	All criteria met through desktop subjective scoring
Automatic classification using secondary data	Acceptable	All criteria met. No manual classification available.

CONVERTING DIFFERENT ASSESSMENT METRICS

We apply consistent ecosystem state metrics for net impact accounting in surface area-adjusted-for-state or “surface area equivalents” (e.g. hectares equivalents or ha eq.). These surface area equivalents are calculated by multiplying the surface area of a polygon (ha) by the relevant ecosystem state score, divided by a reference ecosystem state score (Figure 7.1).

The reference state constitutes the maximum potential state score for an ecosystem (i.e. pre-industrial impact state or minimally affected by human disturbance).

Calculating surface area equivalents (ha eq.)

Figure 7.1. Calculation for surface area equivalents (ha eq.).2

Once ecosystem state scores are produced (using any of the three approaches described in Section 4), we convert different metrics into a single surface area equivalent metric (hectares equivalents) to measure ecosystem gains and losses. For instance, some methods rank ecosystem state categories from A to F (conversion into numerical categories required), while others have continuous scores from 0 to 1 (readily usable) (examples illustrated in Table 7.1 below, adapted from (Houdet & Teren 2022)). This allows for the aggregation of results across sites, without losing the information specific to each ecosystem type or polygon of uniform state score. We record the confidence level of ecosystem state data associated with each polygon (see Section 8.5).

Table 7.1. Example of conversion of different state assessment metrics into a single surface area equivalents metric for consolidation purposes.

Ecosystem type	Area (ha)	Current state score (Time X)					State-adjusted surface area (ha eq.)	
		Method/ Data Source	Current score	Reference state	A	B	area [(ha) x (A/B)].	
					Converted state score (if needed)	Converted reference score (if needed)	Conversion calculation	ha eq.
Vaal-Vet Sandy Grassland	273.95	NDVI	10%-40%	85%+	1	5	273.95 x (1/5)	54.79
Western Free State Clay Grassland	180.57	NDVI	10%-40%	85%+	1	5	180.57 x (1/5)	36.11
Highveld Alluvial Wetland	125.08	WET-Health	B	A	4	5	125.08 x (4/5)	100.06
Vaal-Vet Sandy Grassland (riparian)	19.90	WET-Health	F	A	0	5	19.90 x (0/5)	0.00
Vaal-Vet Sandy Grassland (terrestrial)	1597.21	MSA	0.25	1	0.25	1	1597.21 x (0.25/1)	399.30
Namaqualand Heuweltjie Strandveld	435.50	1-10 survey based	7	10	7	10	435.50 x (7/10)	304.85
Coastal fynbos	500.00	Broad terrestrial ecosystem state scoring system (Table 3)	3	6	3	6	500.00 x (3/6)	250.00
Melaleuca quinquenervia open forest on coastal alluvium (12.3.5)	9.16	BioCondition (see case study in <i>Measuring Ecosystem State for Biodiversity Footprints</i>)	8.34	10	8.34	12	9.16 x (8.34/12)	6.65
Eucalyptus grandis tall open forest on alluvial plains (12.3.2)	3.38	BioCondition (see case study in <i>Measuring Ecosystem State for Biodiversity Footprints</i>)	8.95	10	8.95	12	3.38 x (8.95/12)	2.39
Total	3144.75						Total ha eq.	1154.15

STEPS FOR MESA

There are six main steps to assess ecosystem state (Figure 8.1):

Step 1: Delineation of assessment area.

Step 2: Determine original ecosystems including extent, realm, and reference state context.

Step 3: Delineate patches of uniform state and disturbance.

Step 4: Assess the state of ecosystems using available data or broad scoring tables (Tables 5.1 and 5.2), noting confidence.

Step 5: Create Ecosystem State Asset Register at Time X.

Step 6: Monitor changes in state over time when triggers occur.

Figure 8.1. The six steps of MESA.

Step 1. Delineation of assessment area

An assessment area is typically based on the direct operations of an organisation (operational control / ownership), unless a project-based or broader landscape approach is warranted. The direct operations are defined by the boundaries of all properties where an organisation directly or indirectly controls and directs the day-to-day management and operation of the entity engaging in such activity, whether by contract or otherwise.

The following are key considerations and actions required during this step:

- ▶ We source clear boundaries of direct operations in GIS file format (e.g. .shp or .kmz).
- ▶ These include landholdings owned, leased, or controlled/managed. Typically, areas of rights are excluded if third parties conduct operations on the surface.
- ▶ We evaluate provided boundaries to ensure no errors in geometry or projection.
- ▶ We may apply an ecologically appropriate buffer for linear infrastructure (e.g. an artificial buffer of 50 metres on either side of a pipeline).

Step 2. Determine original ecosystems

- ▶ Original ecosystems refer to the original extent of ecosystems that existed in an area, prior to any human influence or disturbance. We typically source this information from public databases at a country level (see Table 8.1). This applies to freshwater, marine and terrestrial realms (see the case study in *Measuring Ecosystem State for Biodiversity Footprints*).
- ▶ We exclude land use categories (e.g., agriculture, urban areas, roads, managed / plantation forests) or anthropogenically-derived systems since they are not ecosystem types (see Working Paper: *Measuring Ecosystem State for Biodiversity Footprints* for further information).
- ▶ We recognise that original ecosystem extent boundaries contain inherent uncertainty, especially in landscapes with a long history of human modification; however, the underlying abiotic conditions (geology, topography, climate etc.) may be used to determine coarse-scale original ecosystem delineation.
- ▶ When no ecosystem map is available, we make informed assumptions of ecosystem extent using « semi-natural » or « natural » areas nearby, under the same climatic conditions using the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology² Global Ecoregions³ as references.
- ▶ We recognise that most ecosystems identified encompass broad areas that include both terrestrial and aquatic realm components (e.g. rivers, streams, mangroves).
- ▶ We separate realms in the ecosystem asset inventory because management and monitoring requirements differ between terrestrial and aquatic realms. We structure the final impact inventory (or asset register) as a list of ecosystem types at the same classification level, broken down by realm categories and associated surface area information.

² Macfarlane, D., Ollis, D. and Kotze, D. (2020) *WET-Health (Version 2.0). A REFINED SUITE OF TOOLS FOR ASSESSING THE PRESENT ECOLOGICAL STATE OF WETLAND ECOSYSTEMS - TECHNICAL GUIDE* - WATER RESEARCH COMMISSION, South Africa.

³ PES scores and categories to be used where available.

Table 8.1. A selection of national original ecosystem extent sources (Note this is not an exhaustive list and is constantly updated).

Country	File	Source
Argentina	Ecosistemas Terrestres de Argentina	Data Basin
Australia - New South Wales	NSW State Vegetation Type Map (Pre-Clearing)	The SEED Initiative - NSW
Australia - Northern Territory	Vegetation Survey of McArthur River Catchment, Northern Territory	Open Data Portal - Northern Territory
Australia - Queensland	Biodiversity status of pre-clearing	Open Data Portal – Queensland Government
Australia - Western Australia	Pre-European Vegetation – Western Australia (NVIS Compliant version 20110715)	dataWA
Brazil	Vegetation map 2021	IBGE
Canada	2020 Land Cover of Canada	GEO.CA
Chile	Antofagasta Region (II)	IDE
Colombia	MAPA DE ECOSISTEMAS CONTINENTALES COSTEROSY MARINOS DE COLOMBIA VERSIÓN 2.1	SIAC
Germany	World Terrestrial Ecosystems	U.S. Geological Survey
Peru	MAPA_NACIONAL_DE_ECOSISTEMAS_20-12-2018.shp	geo servidor
South Africa	Red List of Ecosystems 2021	SANBI
Other Regions: including New Caledonia, Kazakhstan, Spain and Philippines	Ecoregions 2017	RESOLVE

Step 3. Delineate uniform state and disturbance

- ▶ To produce patches of uniform ecosystem state, we delineate major built and linear infrastructure across the landscape. We also delineate intensive monoculture agriculture. This provides areas of transformation and reveals a coarse level of fragmentation in remnant areas.
- ▶ We further use indicators of land-use or disturbance to delineate remnant areas into patches of uniform state. For example, we may separate areas of a dam and downstream of a dam within a river course; or areas of anthropogenic clearing in a woodland.

Step 4. Score ecosystem state

For terrestrial systems:

- ▶ We use the defined Ecosystem State broad scoring categories out of 6 as per Table 5.1:
 - All completely transformed built-environment areas score 0 (e.g., roads, buildings, mines, quarries).
 - Dams or diversions on terrestrial areas are artificial and score 0: i.e. the terrestrial ecosystem has been completely transformed.
 - Monoculture agriculture areas score 0.05. (Close to zero to mark these areas as nearly completely transformed, with the small non-zero value preserving a marginal residual ecological role relative to fully sealed surfaces (which score 0))
 - For semi- and natural areas, two options are available:
- ▶ If ecological surveys are available, we make sure they fulfil the five criteria in Section 3 for those patches, noting down reference values (e.g. field monitoring data may give an area a 40% score, so we use 40 as the state and 100 as the reference value.). Most importantly there needs to be a quantitative or ranked ecosystem or habitat integrity scoring system that is compatible with Table 3 or can be converted into a similar scoring system.
- ▶ For areas of field data which fulfil most, but not all criteria, we use these data for relevant polygons or slightly adapt the score when, for instance, the historical reference state is missing from the survey approach.
- ▶ If no ecological survey is available for terrestrial ecosystems, we use satellite imagery and available monitoring data on the ecosystem type (e.g. information on alien invasive plant cover), patch size and fragmentation are primary information sources to determine state as per Table 5.1.

For freshwater ecosystems:

- ▶ We use the defined Present Ecological State broad scoring categories out of 6 as used in Table 5.2.
- ▶ Freshwater ecological surveys are often conducted at specific discrete points along a river, so we typically have to extrapolate these results to obtain scores for independent patches. These patches usually shift where water structure or chemistry is affected (see next point).
- ▶ If no ecological survey is available, we rely on satellite imagery and available literature on the ecosystem type (e.g. presence of artificial barrier along river course, upstream or downstream dams, wetland fragmentation).

For every polygon of ecosystem state, we record confidence level. Confidence ranges from best to acceptable (Table 6.1). For polygons which are visibly identifiable as completely transformed, scoring 0, the confidence is assigned as 'best'. For all other polygons, the confidence is based on monitoring data which variably fulfils criteria or automatically assigned 'fair' if expert visual assessment of satellite imagery is the source.

Step 5. Create Ecosystem State Asset Register

This is the final step in creating the input data for biodiversity footprint accounting. For every polygon we calculate the surface area (ha) and run data checks.

Each polygon will have the following attributes:

1. Unique identifier to track its state over time,
2. Operation/ Site name,
3. Ecosystem type,
4. Realm (freshwater/terrestrial/marine),
5. Assessment year,
6. Ecosystem State score,
7. Reference State score,
8. Data source (ideally including year),
9. Ecosystem State Confidence level,
10. Area of polygon (ha),
11. Name of assessor.

We also carry out standard GIS geometry validation to ensure basic data quality (e.g. overlaps, geometry errors, projections), while meeting data interoperability needs (e.g. geodatabase format compliance).

Step 6. Monitor changes in state over time when triggers occur

- ▶ We re-assess state as part of regular monitoring or when defined triggers occur.
- ▶ We consider triggers for re-assessment to include land use change, major pollution events and major management changes (such as multi-year alien invasive eradication programmes, restoration activities, or changes in livestock or fire regimes).
- ▶ We recognise that natural disturbances (e.g. fires, floods, herbivory) which form part of normal ecosystem functioning may not trigger a need for re-assessment, unless they result in significant changes in state that would alter a threshold score for that ecosystem.
- ▶ We take seasonality into account, notably the timing of ecological surveys. These should be undertaken at the optimal time for each ecosystem to allow for accurate identification of key species (such as during the flowering season of plants) and detection of key migratory species.
- ▶ We update ecosystem state maps, as well as the Ecosystem Asset Register, whenever changes in ecosystem state are recorded.

Asset Inventory (Ecosystem State Asset Inventory).

Spatially explicit register of ecosystem polygons within an assessment boundary, recording for each polygon its ecosystem type, realm, area, ecosystem state score, reference state score, data source, confidence level, and assessor. The Asset Inventory is the input dataset for biodiversity footprint accounting under the BD Protocol.

Baseline.

Starting point against which subsequent changes in ecosystem state are measured. Baselines are arbitrary, set by policy, management or business context, and are distinct from reference states (Bedford *et al.* 2023; McNellie *et al.* 2020).

BD Protocol (Biological Diversity Protocol).

Standardised accounting framework for identifying, measuring, recording, compiling and disclosing organisational biodiversity impacts on ecosystems and material species (Endangered Wildlife Trust 2020).

Biodiversity Footprint (BF).

The total impact of an organisation, project, region, service or product on biodiversity, comprising a Total, Positive and Negative Biodiversity Footprint (TBF, PBF, NBF) under the BD Protocol.

Confidence level.

A label (Best, Better, Good, Fair, Acceptable) recorded for each ecosystem state data input in MESA, reflecting how many of the five accounting quality criteria the data source meets (Table 6.1).

Ecological integrity.

A condition that supports intact species assemblages and ecological processes in their natural state, relative to an appropriate historical benchmark, characterised by contiguous natural habitat with minimal direct industrial anthropogenic disturbance (IUCN, 2016).

Ecosystem state.

Where an ecosystem stands, at a given place and time, against its reference situation; described by composition, structure, and function relative to a defined reference state.

Functional integrity.

The ecosystem's current ability to maintain the structure and functions that define it, compared to its known or predicted reference state (South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) 2022) .

Hectares equivalents (ha eq.).

State-adjusted surface area, calculated as polygon area (ha) x (ecosystem state score / reference state score). Used to express ecosystem gains and losses on a comparable scale across ecosystem types and assessment methods.

No Net Loss (NNL) / Net Positive Impact (NPI).

Outcome objectives stating that an organisation's net impact on biodiversity (across the mitigation hierarchy) should be at least zero (NNL) or positive (NPI) over a defined period.

Original ecosystem extent.

The pre-disturbance distribution of ecosystems within an area, used as the spatial baseline for delineating ecosystem types in MESA Step 2.

Polygon.

A bounded spatial unit of uniform ecosystem state used as the elementary record in the Ecosystem State Asset Inventory.

Present Ecological State (PES).

The perceived deviation of a freshwater ecosystem from a theoretical reference condition, where the reference condition is defined as the un-impacted condition in which ecosystems show little or no influence of human actions (Macfarlane *et al.* 2020)

Realm.

Major component of the living natural world (terrestrial, freshwater, marine, subterranean, atmospheric) per the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology (Keith *et al.* 2020, 2022).

Reference state.

The ecological context against which ecosystem state is evaluated. Reference states may be historical (pre-industrial) or contemporary (present-day, best-on-offer, best-of-what's-left), and must be recorded explicitly with each MESA assessment (McNellie *et al.* 2020).

Surface area equivalents.

See Hectares equivalents (ha eq.).

- Bedford, J., Calhoun, E., Brooks, S., Houdet, J., Berger, J. & Grigg, A. (2023). *Measuring Ecosystem Condition – A primer for business, Aligning accounting approaches for nature*. UNEP-WCMC, Capitals Coalition, Arcadis, ICF, WCMC Europe.
- Endangered Wildlife Trust. (2020). *The Biological Diversity Protocol (BD Protocol)*. National Biodiversity and Business Network - South Africa.
- Eyre., T.J., Kelly, A.L., Neldner, V.J., Wilson, B.A., Fergusson, D.J., Laidlaw, M.J., et al. (2015). *BioCondition: A Condition Assessment Framework for Terrestrial Biodiversity in Queensland. Assessment Manual*. (No. Version 2.2). Queensland Herbarium, Science Delivery.
- Houdet, J. & Teren, G. (2022). *QUALITY BIODIVERSITY FOOTPRINT ASSESSMENTS IN PRACTICE. Why organisational biodiversity accounting matters*. (A Position Paper of the Biodiversity Disclosure Project (BDP)). National Biodiversity and Business Network, Endangered Wildlife Trust, South Africa.
- IUCN. (2016). A Global Standard for the Identification of Key Biodiversity Areas, Version 1.0.
- Keith, D.A., Ferrer-Paris, J.R., Nicholson, E., Bishop, M.J., Polidoro, B.A., Ramirez-Llodra, E., et al. (2022). A function-based typology for Earth's ecosystems. *Nature*, 610, 513–518.
- Keith, D.A., Ferrer-Paris, J.R., Nicholson, E. & Kingsford, R.T. (Eds.). (2020). *IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology 2.0: descriptive profiles for biomes and ecosystem functional groups*. IUCN, International Union for Conservation of Nature.
- Macfarlane, D., Ollis, D. & Kotze, D. (2020). *WET-Health (Version 2.0) A REFINED SUITE OF TOOLS FOR ASSESSING THE PRESENT ECOLOGICAL STATE OF WETLAND ECOSYSTEMS -- TECHNICAL GUIDE* -. WATER RESEARCH COMMISSION.
- McNellie, M.J., Oliver, I., Dorrrough, J., Ferrier, S., Newell, G. & Gibbons, P. (2020). Reference state and benchmark concepts for better biodiversity conservation in contemporary ecosystems. *Global Change Biology*, 26, 6702–6714.
- South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI). (2022). *Species Environmental Assessment Guideline. Guidelines for the implementation of the Terrestrial Fauna and Terrestrial Flora Species Protocols for environmental impact assessments in South Africa. Version 3.1*.

ABOUT THE BIODIVERSITY FOOTPRINT COMPANY

The Biodiversity Footprint Company (TBFC) is a research and consulting organisation dedicated to advancing biodiversity accounting and conservation.

Our Vision

To be the **reference** in biodiversity footprinting by providing **transparent, evidence-backed, and actionable insights** that help businesses move beyond greenwashing into real, measurable impact. We envision a future where **biodiversity accounting is as rigorous as financial reporting**, equipping organizations with the tools to navigate complexity, set meaningful targets, and take credible action for nature.

Our Mission

We cut through the noise, demystifying biodiversity measurement and strategy with **deep insight and scientific integrity**. Our work empowers corporations, municipalities, financial institutions, and policymakers with the **clarity and confidence** to make informed, responsible decisions that align with ecological reality.

Fast facts

- ∞ We are pioneers in the biodiversity and business field, working with clients for over a decade.
- ∞ We are a small consultancy which focuses on providing agile solutions through hands-on expert knowledge from the directors in every project and staying ahead of the pack through research and development.
- ∞ To date, we have produced high-quality biodiversity footprints in over 17 countries, totalling over 2.2 Million ha and 940 Ecosystems.
- ∞ We have set the benchmark for rigorous biodiversity accounting as the lead authors of the Biological Diversity Protocol (BD Protocol) recommended by the TNFD, SBTN, and GRI.

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